

MEASURES TO SOLVE ENVIRONMENTAL PROBLEMS

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Abstract. *The article presents information about the functions of ecotechnologies based on biotechnology. It is essential to develop biotechnology for a healthy lifestyle. This allows us to monitor the development of environmental safety indicators and environmental factors that are harmful to human health.*

With the help of modern eco-technologies, it is possible to protect the ecosystem from various threats, regulating sustainable development.

Keywords: *Medicine, bioecotechnology, environment, control, bioresources, energy, protection, bioecology, ecocommies, organization, pests, ecosystem.*

Аннотация. *В статье представлена информация о функциях экотехнологий, основанных на биотехнологиях. Необходимо развивать сферу биотехнологий для здорового образа жизни. Это позволяет контролировать развитие показателей экологической безопасности и экологических факторов, наносящих вред здоровью человека.*

С помощью современных экотехнологий можно защитить экосистему от различных угроз, регулируя устойчивое развитие.

Ключевые слова: *Медицина, биоэкология, окружающая среда, контроль, биоресурсы, энергия, защита, биоэкология, экомии, организация, вредители, экосистема.*

Annotatsiya. *Mazkur maqola biotexnologiyaga asoslangan ekotexnologiyalarning vazifalari to'g'risida ma'lumotlar beradi. Sog'lom turmush tarzi uchun biotexnologiya sohasini rivojlantirish zarur. Bu esa ekologik xavfsizlik ko'rsatkichlarining rivojlanishini va insonning sog'lig'iga zarar keltiruvchi ekoomillarni nazoratga oladi. Zamon talabiga mos ekotexnologiyalar yordamida, barqaror rivojlanishni tartibga solish orqali ekotizmni turli xafvlardan saqlash mumkin.*

Kalit so'zlar: *Tibbiyot, bioekotexnologiya, atrof-muhit, nazorat, bioresurs, energiya, nazorat, himoya, bioekologiya, ecoomilar, tashkilot, zararkunanda, ekotizm.*

In developing countries, environmental problems are also becoming more acute due to economic development. This requires urgent solutions. To overcome environmental challenges, a systematization of economic methods based on the experience of global scientists is necessary. This will help determine the direction of environmental policy.

Ecotechnologies are methods developed on the basis of biotechnology, they can also be called “green” or “ecological” biotechnologies.

To prevent unsustainable development of environmental safety indicators, it is necessary to stimulate the development of biotechnology. In rapidly developing countries, the use of environmental factors that affect human health must be controlled. To solve environmental problems, it is necessary to develop biotechnology. Because ecotechnologies can help regulate sustainable development.

Thus, based on the above, it can be said that ecotechnologies based on biotechnology serve to regulate environmental sustainability.

Ecotechnologies manage waste that enters the environment in various ways. They also monitor the use of biotechnology to create environmentally friendly solutions. It is necessary to develop the necessary programs for environmental protection using eco-technologies created on the basis of biotechnology. This will bring atmospheric pollution under control.

Biotechnology also creates technologies for various fields, such as medicine and agriculture. Such ecotechnologies use bioecological principles to manage environmental sustainability.

The environmentally friendly application of ecobiotechnology ensures environmental sustainability. This allows us to address various environmental issues. That is, it reduces pollution through effective management of ecosystems. It controls the release of waste from various organizations into the environment.

Based on the above, it can be said that biotechnology controls harmful substances to human health. At the same time, it determines the regulatory parameters of substances used for pests in agriculture. It also serves to improve industry and protect the environment.

In rapidly developing countries, there is a need to promote ecosystem management technologies to reduce environmental pollution.

Therefore, it is essential to exert maximum control over processes that harm the environment. It is essential to utilize the resources of enterprises and organizations for waste management as efficiently as possible. To achieve this, measures must be developed to implement a circular economy.

In conclusion, it can be said that biotechnology-based eco-technologies perform unique tasks such as protecting the atmosphere from various unnecessary emissions.

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(8th international scientific and practical conference)

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